

CONTEMPORARY TECHNOLOGIES AND TECHNOLOGICAL RESOURCES FOR THE ORIENTATION OF EXPLORATORY-CORE DRILLING

Boris Patchejeff

University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, 1700 Sofia; E-mail: b.patchejeff@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. In the current paper, the subject of analysis are the current technologies and technical resources used in orientation, spatial position of exploration boreholes. Controlling and directing the trajectory of the process of drilling exploration holes is crucial for successfully reaching of the exploration target. The exact control and determination of trajectory of a borehole is the correct planning and measurement of its direction and the inclination. In the process of drilling, depending on the intensity of borehole deviation, a measurement interval is set. For optimal precision, measurements are done each 30-50 meters with the advancement of the hole. The information processing is done by the Minimum Curvature method and the results are presented in a tabular form and graphically. The focus is on the gyroscopic and magnetic methods of borehole orientation, along with their advantages and disadvantages.

Key words: directional, exploratory-core drilling, orientation, survey.

СЪВРЕМЕННИ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ И ТЕХНИЧЕСКИ СРЕДСТВА ЗА ОРИЕНТАЦИЯ НА ПРОУЧВАТЕЛНО-ЯДКОВИ СОНДАЖИ

Борис Пачеджиев

Минно-геоложки университет „Св. Иван Рилски“, 1700 София

РЕЗЮМЕ. В настоящия доклад са анализирани съвременните технологии и технически средства за ориентирани и измерване на пространственото положение на проучвателни сондажи. Контролирането и насочването на траекторията в процеса на прокарване на проучвателни сондажи е изключително важно за успешното достигане до основния хоризонт на проучване. Точното контролиране и определяне траекторията на сондажа е правилното измерване на инклинацията и азимута. В процеса на сондиране, в зависимост от интензитета на изкривяване на сондажа се задава честотата на измерването. За точно измерване в практиката се извършва на всеки 30-50 метра. За обработка на измерените параметри се използва методът на минималната крива, като резултатите се представят таблично и графично. Обърнато е внимание на използваните методи за ориентирани, които са жирокопичен и магнитен метод и техните предимства и недостатъци.

Ключови думи: насочено, проучвателно-ядрово сондиране, ориентация, измерване.

Introduction

The technology of diamond core drilling differs from other drilling methods, since during its passage along the entire profile of the well, a cylindrical core sample (core) is extracted to the surface. The main rock-breaking tool is the diamond bit shown in Fig. 1. It consists of industrial diamonds impregnated in a tungsten-carbide matrix which, depending on the geological conditions, has different hardness and chemical content. The diamonds are fixed, according to a certain scheme, throughout the matrix, as in the drilling process, the entire matrix is subjected to wear. In case of improper operation of the crown, it can wear out in a very short time if the recommended drilling parameters are not followed (axial pressure, RPM, flow rate of the drilling fluid) or very difficult rock conditions were encountered.

Fig. 1. Diamond core bit
([https://epiroc.scene7.com/is/image/epiroc/image-matrix-background-1902x1365?%\\$landscape1600\\$](https://epiroc.scene7.com/is/image/epiroc/image-matrix-background-1902x1365?%$landscape1600$))

The diamond bit Fig. 1. is put into the lower (front) part of the outer core tube shown in Fig.2.

Description of Fig.2 elements are as it follows:

1. Head assembly
2. Inner tube
3. Stop-ring
4. Core lifter
5. Core case
6. Bronze centralizer
7. Landing ring
8. Core barrel (outer tube)
9. Reamer (blank)

The drilling fluid is pumped into the drilling tool, by a pump, through a swivel, mounted to the upper part of the drilling rod, in order to clean the drilling cuttings, cool the bit, (which leads to less friction, wear, and deformation of the diamonds and the matrix), stabilise the drill rods, and maintain an optimal percentage of extracted core, according to the requirements of the client. For each specific site, it is necessary to prepare a hydraulic program. In diamond drilling, it is advisable to use polymer solutions, even though in some regions bentonite disperse systems are preferred. (Todorov et al., 2009).

Fig. 2. Core barrel and inner tube
(<https://timeltd.ca/products/drilling-and-exploration/>)

The drilling rig creates the necessary axial load and rotation frequency on the diamond bit during the drilling process. Subsequently, part of the rock formation (the so-called core), depending on the internal diameter of the diamond core according to the IADC standard, enters the core inner tube (Fig. 2[2]). It is brought to the surface by means of an overshot, which engages the bearing body, which is wound in the upper part of the inner core tube shown in Fig. 2[1]. The bearing body has the function of holding the core tube in a locked position from its lower part during drilling, and from its upper part (above the bearings) to rotate together with the drilling rod shown in Fig. 2[1]. The core case (Fig. 2[5]), spring (Fig. 2[4]), and stop-ring (Fig. 2[3]) serve to grip and break the core sample. The outer core tube (Fig. 2[8]) consists of a bronze centraliser, centering the inner tube (Fig. 2[9]), a stop ring, where the bearing body stops (Fig. 2[7]), an adapter or reamer (Fig. 2[6]) and a locking coupling, where the latches of the bearing body are engaged.

Borehole surveying

Inclinometry is a method for determining the spatial position of boreholes at depth and graphically displaying its trajectory. It is also used to accurately determine the location and orientation of other tools used in the drilling process (positioning of wedges, orientation of directional drilling tools, etc.).

During drilling, it is necessary to survey the borehole in order to determine and control its spatial position. For this purpose, specialised measurement systems have been created and have been used for many years, the main improvement and refinement being the accuracy of the instruments employed and their simplification for use.

One of these instruments is a multishot survey tool, which is relatively cheap and simple to operate, taking into account that the magnetism of the layers and the surrounding equipment is low enough not to disturb it.

On the other hand, gyroscopic instruments are widely used in drilling, being significantly more expensive, but not affected by magnetic environments. Another advantage of the gyroscope is that it can perform a continuous survey. This reduces the overlap of stations in the magnetic survey, which better describes the trajectory of the borehole.

Magnetic EMS		North-finding gyroscope	
Magnetic field X	B_x	\leftrightarrow	Earth rate X Ω_x
Magnetic field Y	B_y	\leftrightarrow	Earth rate Y Ω_y
Magnetic field Z	B_z	\leftrightarrow	Earth rate Z Ω_z
Magnetic field total	B	\leftrightarrow	Earth rate total Ω
Magnetic dip	D_m	\leftrightarrow	Latitude $-\varphi$
Inclination from vertical	I	\leftrightarrow	Inclination from vertical I
Highside	H	\leftrightarrow	Highside H

Fig. 3. Variables included in the mathematical model of gyroscopic and magnetic survey tools (Billger, 2019)

These are divided into two main groups using physical measurements, the Earth's magnetic field, and its rotation speed, as their principle of operation is mathematically identical (shown in Fig. 3).

Therefore, the limitations of magnetic survey tools are also found in non-magnetic (gyroscopes).

Inclinometry measures elements of the curvature of the borehole at certain depths. These elements include:

- angle of inclination (borehole inclination) - the angle between the vertical and the borehole axis. In this regard, in exploratory drilling, a vertical borehole is assumed to be -90 degrees, and a horizontal borehole has a slope value of 0 degrees;
 - magnetic azimuth (Magnetic North) - the angle between the horizontal projection of the borehole axis and magnetic north;
 - geographic azimuth (True North) - the angle between the horizontal projection of the borehole axis and geographic north.
- It is also important to mention the Grid North – the convergent angle between true True North and Grid North, for aligning the instrument's north when using the UTM system shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Types of north (Jamieson, 2017)

Data on the deviation rate are necessary for:

- controlling the preservation of the trajectory set in the project;
- controlling the avoidance of sharp deviations of the well, which can cause complications during drilling;
- obtaining the necessary initial data for the compilation of geological and geophysical sections, diagrams and maps (determining the position and depth of the elements in the section of the well - layers, face, etc.).

The main geological reasons that cause the deviation of the well are the different hardness of the rocks being drilled and their layering, as well as the significant angle of inclination of the layers.

The main technological reason is non-compliance with the operating parameters.

Surveying interval

The deviation rate of the borehole is measured by DLS (DogLeg Severity), and the minimum curvature method is used for its calculation. The minimum curvature method assumes that the borehole path between two consecutive geodetic stations can be approximated by a segment of a circular arc shown in Fig. 5.

For a specific average deviation intensity, it follows that the optimal borehole measurement interval for trajectory control is between 30 and 50 meters. As a good practice, this measurement is multishot, which is a technique for determining the deflection of a borehole shaft. The Continuous measurement technique is also popular. The multishot tool provides greater accuracy than the singleshot one. In practice, the Continuous measurement technique is used, as measured in borehole 2. To perform a continuous gyroscopic

Another important factor in this type of measurements is the value of the magnetic field, measured in nanoteslas, as a difference of over 1000nT means that the measurement is compromised by magnetic interference. (Billger, 2021)

In borehole 2, where the measurement is made with a gyroscope, to avoid errors and compromising measurements, the gyroscope must be kept in oscillation mode (amplification) and the measurement speed set by the manufacturer (m/min) must be observed, in order to achieve optimal oscillation of the device.

Conclusion

Proper setting and surveying in the borehole during the drilling process are the conditions for a correct trajectory and falling within the radius of the set target. It is necessary that the measurement interval be every 30-50 meters to monitor the trajectory. The correct technology for measuring and setting the direction when drilling exploration boreholes must be known and followed.

Literature

Billger, Dag. (2019). Similarities between magnetic and north-finding survey tools. *Coring Magazine*, Issue 9.

- Billger, Dag. (2020). Comparing multishot & continuous surveys using the TwinGyro™. *Coring Magazine*, Issue 12.
- Billger, Dag. (2021). Technical interview with Dag Billger and Duncan McLeod. *Coring Magazine*, Issue 15.
- Dimovski, S. (2007). *Rakovodstvo za prakticheski zanyatiya po sondazhna geofizika*. Sofia.
- Jamieson, Angus. (2017). Introduction to wellbore positioning. V06.02.2017
- Todorov, I., Harizanov, M., Stoykov, S. (2009). Drilling technology and usage of polymer drilling fluids for mineral exploration diamond core drilling applications in the Chelopech Cu-Au deposit (Bulgaria). *Annual of the University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski"*, 52, Part I, Geology and Geophysics, pp. 189-193. ISSN 1312-1820.
- <https://epiroc.scene7.com/is/image/epiroc/image-matrix-background-1902x1365?landscape1600>
- https://glossary.slb.com/terms/m/multishot_survey#:~:text=1.%20n.%20%5BReservoir%20Characterization,used%20in%20highly%20deviated%20wells.
- <https://timeltd.ca/products/drilling-and-exploration/>
- <https://unacademy.com/content/nda/study-material/mathematics/analytical-geometry-three-dimensions-distance-between-two-points/>
- <https://www.drillingformulas.com/minimum-curvature-method/>